

ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE ON PREVENTION OF LEPTOSPIROSIS WITH THE USE OF DOXYCYCLINE AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS IN PAMPANGA: BASIS FOR HEALTH PROMOTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Leptospirosis is a zoonotic disease caused by pathogenic bacteria of the genus *Leptospira*. This infection is managed by early detection and management through the available preventive measures. Although precautions are available, the drastic increase in cases has been noted globally and locally in recent years. Immediate action must be implemented promptly to address and eliminate the growing threat of Leptospirosis outbreaks and the increase in cases. This study aimed to assess the level of knowledge among college students in Pampanga regarding the use of doxycycline as prophylaxis for leptospirosis prevention. A quantitative descriptive study with correlational and comparative components was utilized as a research design. A purposive sampling method was employed to recruit the 377 respondents aged 18 to 24 years old from college schools in Pampanga. Data were collected using a researchers' made questionnaire, statistical analysis was conducted using measures of central tendency by the use of mean \pm standard deviation. The t-test for independent samples and Pearson's *r* correlation were applied to determine the difference in the level of knowledge when grouped in the context of demographic profile. Results indicated a generally low level of

knowledge among college students regarding the use of doxycycline prophylaxis, emphasizing the need for targeted health education initiatives. In response, a health promotion program was created to improve public awareness of the effective utilization of doxycycline for preventing leptospirosis. This study highlights the critical need for educational interventions to improve disease prevention efforts and strengthen public health strategies in combating leptospirosis.

Keywords: *Doxycycline, Knowledge, Leptospirosis, Outbreaks, Pathogenic, Prophylaxis*

INTRODUCTION

Leptospirosis is a life-threatening zoonotic disease caused by *Leptospira* species, transmitted through direct or indirect exposure to contaminated water, soil, or animal urine. The disease is particularly prevalent in tropical and subtropical regions, where environmental conditions favor bacterial survival (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2024). In the Philippines, leptospirosis remains a significant public health concern, particularly in flood-prone areas. The Department of Health (DOH, 2023) reported a 75% increase in cases, with 4,274 infections and 477 deaths recorded from January to September 2023, compared to 2,446 cases in the same period the previous year. The rising incidence highlights the urgent need for effective preventive strategies to mitigate infection risks.

One of the most widely recommended preventive measures is doxycycline prophylaxis, which has been proven effective in reducing leptospirosis infection rates. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2003) and the CDC (2024) advocate for doxycycline administration in high-risk individuals, particularly during floods or after exposure to potentially contaminated environments. A single 200 mg dose of doxycycline can reduce leptospirosis risk by up to 95% (Gompf, 2021). Despite its effectiveness, public awareness and utilization of doxycycline as a preventive measure remain low, particularly among young adults (Fonseka et al., 2019).

College students are an at-risk population due to their frequent travel, exposure to urban floodwaters, and limited access to health information on leptospirosis prevention. Studies indicate that knowledge gaps regarding leptospirosis prevention exist among students, influencing their risk perception and adherence to prophylactic measures (Rajakakse, 2022). In Pampanga, where seasonal flooding is common, assessing students' awareness of doxycycline prophylaxis is crucial in developing targeted health education campaigns.

This study aims to evaluate the level of knowledge among college students in Pampanga regarding the use of doxycycline as prophylaxis for leptospirosis. Using a quantitative descriptive research design, this study seeks to identify knowledge gaps and determine whether demographic factors (age, gender, academic background) influence awareness levels. The researchers of this study believe that understanding these gaps

will provide a foundation for evidence-based health promotion initiatives, ensuring that students are better informed about leptospirosis prevention.

By bridging this research gap, the findings of this study can help develop targeted health education programs, encouraging proper utilization of doxycycline prophylaxis and ultimately reducing the incidence of leptospirosis among at-risk populations. The results may also serve as a reference for public health authorities and educational institutions in designing more effective leptospirosis awareness campaigns, emphasizing the role of prophylaxis in disease prevention.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the level of knowledge of college students in Pampanga regarding the use of doxycycline prophylaxis for the prevention of leptospirosis. Specifically, the research seeks to answer the following questions:

- 1.) How may the respondents be described as to;
 - 1.1) Age
 - 1.2) Sex
 - 1.3) Course
 - 1.4) Type of Course
 - 1.5) General Weighted Average (last semester)
 - 1.6) History of leptospirosis
 - 1.7) Perception of Risk and
 - 1.8) Awareness Activity on Leptospirosis
 - 1.9) Awareness on Doxycycline chemoprophylaxis;

- 2.) What is the level of knowledge of the respondents regarding the use of doxycycline as prophylaxis for leptospirosis;

- 3.) What is the relationship of the level of awareness and the socio-demographic variables of the respondents (age, GWA, sex, and course);

- 4.) Based on the results of the study, what is the most appropriate health promotion plan for college students on the use of doxycycline as a prophylaxis for leptospirosis?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a quantitative research methodology, specifically a descriptive design with correlational and comparative components. These designs aimed to systematically investigate relationships among variables without manipulation, providing insights into trends and associations.

The participants were college students from Pampanga. Data collection was conducted via social media platforms by disseminating a social media card and engaging acquaintances from other colleges in the region. Respondents were provided informed consent before completing a questionnaire through Google Forms, which required approximately 10–20 minutes to complete. Privacy measures ensured that data access was restricted to researchers, and respondent identities remained anonymous.

The research instrument was a researchers' made questionnaire. The development was guided by the standard set by the Department of Health (DOH) and underwent validation by three experts: a program manager, a medical doctor, and a health education officer. A pilot study involving 30 college students was conducted to refine the questionnaire. Reliability testing yielded an excellent internal consistency score ($\alpha=0.934$), confirming its robustness. A Cronbach's alpha above 0.9 is regarded as indicative of excellent reliability.

Data analysis utilized Google Sheets and R Studio software (version 4.2.1). Descriptive statistics summarized categorical variables (e.g., sex, course) using frequencies and percentages, while quantitative variables (e.g., age, general weighted average) were reported as mean \pm standard deviation. The normal distribution of data was verified through histogram plots. Inferential analyses included t-tests for comparing knowledge scores between groups (e.g., sex and course) and Pearson's r for correlating continuous variables like age and general weighted average.

Bloom's cutoff criteria categorized knowledge scores into low, moderate, and high levels based on statistical results. Statistical tests were conducted at a 5% significance level with Bonferroni corrections to account for multiple comparisons. This methodological approach ensured the reliability and validity of findings while maintaining ethical standards in data handling.

This research paper particularly aims to assess the level of knowledge in doxycycline as prophylaxis for leptospirosis among the college students in Pampanga. Certainly, the main focus of this study is to determine if the college students have knowledge about the use of doxycycline as a prophylaxis for leptospirosis during flood season. Only the college students will be included in the study.

RESULTS

The collected data was arranged, totaled, and examined in accordance with the objectives of the study. Both textual and tabular presentations of the collected data are made.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents.

	M	SD
Age	20.29	1.312
General weighted average	88.87	5.121

	n	%
Sex		
Male	134	35.17%
Female	247	64.83%
Course		
Science	249	65.35%
Non-science	132	34.65%
Have you or your immediate family gotten leptospirosis before? (*History of leptospirosis)		
Yes	24	6.30%
No	357	93.70%
Do you consider yourself at risk for leptospirosis? (*Perception of risk)		
Yes	92	24.15%
No	289	75.85%
Have you attended any leptospirosis related awareness activity? (*Awareness Activity on Leptospirosis)		
Yes	44	11.55%
No	337	88.45%
Have you heard about the use of doxycycline in preventing leptospirosis? (*Awareness on Doxycycline chemoprophylaxis)		
Yes	117	30.71%
No	264	69.29%

Table 2.1. Frequency distribution of correct answers of doxycycline use among respondents according to per item.

	n	%
1. Leptospirosis is acquired through water or soil contaminated with infected animal urine when in contact with skin, especially if there is abrasion or presence of wound.		
Correct	367	96.33%
Wrong	14	3.67%
I do not know	0	0.00%
2. High fever, headache, chills, muscle aches, vomiting, jaundice (yellow skin and eyes), red eyes, abdominal pain, diarrhea and rash are the most common signs and symptoms of leptospirosis.		
Correct	337	88.45%
Wrong	41	10.76%
I do not know	3	0.79%

3. Wearing boots or protective footwear when wading in dirty flood water or in potentially contaminated bodies of freshwater are basic prevention for leptospirosis.		
Correct	370	97.11%
Wrong	11	2.89%
I do not know	0	0.00%
4. Doxycycline is a type of antiprotozoal drug that is used for leptospirosis prevention.		
Correct	188	49.34%
Wrong	20	5.25%
I do not know	173	45.41%
5. Doxycycline can be accessed for free in government health facilities such as rural health units and hospitals.		
Correct	157	41.21%
Wrong	213	55.91%
I do not know	11	2.89%
6. Doxycycline as prophylaxis can be given sublingually.		
Correct	121	31.76%
Wrong	29	7.61%
I do not know	231	60.63%
7. Leptospirosis can be transmitted through contaminated water so I must take a single dose of doxycycline after 24-72 hours of being exposed to the flood.		
Correct	179	46.98%
Wrong	177	46.46%
I do not know	25	6.56%
8. I can take doxycycline even though I have an allergy to other similar antibiotics such as tetracycline.		
Correct	37	9.71%
Wrong	161	42.26%
I do not know	183	48.03%
9. I can take doxycycline if I have liver or kidney disease.		
Correct	45	11.81%
Wrong	125	32.81%
I do not know	211	55.38%
10. Doxycycline can be taken by children 8 years old and above.		
Correct	108	28.35%
Wrong	231	60.63%
I do not know	42	11.02%
11. Herbal remedies can be used together with doxycycline.		
Correct	87	22.83%
Wrong	82	21.52%
I do not know	212	55.64%
12. Doxycycline can be taken by pregnant women.		

Correct	34	8.92%
Wrong	149	39.11%
I do not know	198	51.97%
13. A breastfeeding mother can take doxycycline as it cannot pass into breast milk.		
Correct	54	14.17%
Wrong	123	32.28%
I do not know	204	53.54%
14. Taking doxycycline can make oral contraceptives less effective.		
Correct	73	19.16%
Wrong	248	65.09%
I do not know	60	15.75%
15. I must avoid exposure to sunlight or artificial UV rays when I take doxycycline.		
Correct	127	33.33%
Wrong	227	59.58%
I do not know	27	7.09%
16. I can take doxycycline with dairy products, iron supplements, multivitamins, calcium supplements, and antacids.		
Correct	70	18.37%
Wrong	95	24.93%
I do not know	216	56.69%
17. I can take doxycycline with an empty stomach.		
Correct	73	19.16%
Wrong	133	34.91%
I do not know	175	45.93%
18. I must not take Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) medications such as Ibuprofen and Mefenamic acid while taking doxycycline as it causes stomach ache.		
Correct	137	35.96%
Wrong	217	56.96%
I do not know	27	7.09%
19. I can lie down right after taking doxycycline.		
Correct	67	17.59%
Wrong	105	27.56%
I do not know	209	54.86%
20. Symptoms such as hives, difficulty of breathing, swelling of the face, lips, tongue, or throat are normal side effects of taking doxycycline.		
Correct	94	24.67%
Wrong	71	18.64%
I do not know	215	56.43%

21. Taking anti-diarrheal medications is contraindicated when there's a side effect of diarrhea while taking doxycycline because of possible signs of a new infection.

Correct	139	36.48%
Wrong	224	58.79%
I do not know	18	4.72%

Table 2.2. Overall knowledge score of doxycycline use among respondents.

Category	Scores (%)	n	%
Low	<60%	241	63.25%
Moderate	61%-80%	138	36.22%
High	81%-100%	2	0.52%
		M	SD
Average knowledge score		52.48%	12.44%

Table 3.1. Comparison of knowledge scores according to sex and course.

	Male		Female		t	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Average knowledge score	53.70%	12.64%	51.82%	12.31%	1.406	0.161
	Science		Non-science			
Average knowledge score	49.50%	12.20%	55.10%	12.10%	-1.745	0.082

Table 3.2. Comparison of knowledge scores according to age and general weighted average.

	n	M	SD	1	2	3
1. Total knowledge score	38					
	1			-		
	38					
2. Age	1	20.29	1.312	-.09	-	
3. General weighted average	38					
	0	88.87	5.121	.12*	-.08	-

*p < .05. **p < .01.

DISCUSSION

Leptospirosis is a significant public health concern in tropical regions, particularly during summer and fall, due to frequent heavy rainfall and flooding, which facilitate rapid transmission from infected animals to humans. This disease can lead to severe

complications, including organ damage, systemic illness, and coma. A primary factor contributing to infection is the inconsistent use of available preventive measures, such as doxycycline chemoprophylaxis. Therefore, enhancing knowledge about doxycycline through educational initiatives is crucial. This study examines the level of knowledge regarding doxycycline as a preventive measure against leptospirosis, particularly in Pampanga, while assessing variations across demographic groups among college students. The study's key outcome is the development of a health promotion program to improve college students' understanding of doxycycline use.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

As per the results, the average age of respondents is 20.29 years of age ranging from 18-24 years of age, with an average age of 20.29 years (SD = 1.312). Traditionally, the majority of the age of college students ranges from 18-20 years old (Cebu, 2023). In addition, the general weighted average of the respondents have a score of 83 to 94, with an average score of 88.87 (SD = 5.121) which implies the academic performance of the respondents. In line with this matter, the general weighted average is a reliable metric for assessing a students' level of knowledge and academic performance (Barnacha et al., 2023). In terms of sex, the respondents consisted of 134 male respondents (35.17%) and 247 female respondents (64.83%). This indicates that the majority of the respondents are female. For sex, both female and male possessed general knowledge despite the stereotype dominance of male in cognitive aspects. According to Asante, Ackah, and Frimpong (2023), female and male both excel in academic performance, however, there are other factors that may affect the outcome of academic performance of one sex to another such as methods of teaching, socio-economic, and support from the parents. As for the type of courses, the courses of the respondents are categorized into science and non-science strand. The majority of respondents (65.35%) were from the Science strand, while 34.65% were from the non-science strand.

On the other hand, the history of leptospirosis is included to determine if there is a previous case of having leptospirosis in their family. Almost all respondents (96.59%) reported having heard about leptospirosis. As clearly shown in the findings, the least portion of the respondents (6.30%) having had leptospirosis interprets that majority of the respondents had not been exposed to leptospirosis infection, or with their family. In another variable, perception of risk in acquiring leptospirosis can be a possible factor of contracting the infection during flood. A minority of the respondents considered themselves at risk for acquiring leptospirosis (24.15%), which indicates that their places are not frequently flooded, or not surrounded by rice fields. To the awareness activity in leptospirosis, respondents may already have attended seminars or webinars regarding doxycycline as chemoprophylaxis. Although, a small proportion of the respondents has attended awareness activity on leptospirosis (11.55%), as this expound that there are available activities about leptospirosis. However, the activity still needs to be improved in terms of dissemination in the public. Lastly, awareness on doxycycline as chemoprophylaxis assists to exhibit the recognition of the respondents regarding the existence of doxycycline as prevention of leptospirosis. In this variable, almost half of the respondents had heard the use of doxycycline (30.71%), which serves as an indication

that few of the respondents are already aware.

Level of Knowledge of the Respondents Regarding The Use of Doxycycline As Prophylaxis For Leptospirosis

The results of this study support the assumption that the level of knowledge of a person contributes to the risk of acquiring leptospirosis. In terms of knowledge, the average knowledge score of 52.48% (SD = 12.44%) was identified after summing up the respondents' responses. Based on Bloom's cut-off criteria, this indicates that, on average, college students in Pampanga exhibited a low level of knowledge concerning the prevention of leptospirosis using doxycycline. Although nearly all respondents (370, 97.11%) have a high knowledge level on basic prevention of leptospirosis such as wearing boots or protective footwear, it is important for the public to be more aware of using doxycycline as a chemoprophylaxis when wading in dirty flood water or potentially contaminated bodies of freshwater. Humans do not have natural immunity to leptospirosis, and the disease can be acquired through various routes, including skin abrasions, mucous membranes, and even ingestion of contaminated water which can lead to severe, potentially fatal complications. Antibiotic prophylaxis for leptospirosis is recommended by World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines as a potential preventive measure, especially for travelers and high-risk groups (WHO 2003; Kozue 2022). Mass antibiotic prophylaxis can provide protection by preventing illness and mortality, reducing the number of individuals infected with leptospirosis following a high-risk exposure, and lowering the overall number of infected patients (Goarant 2016; Rahim 2018).

Relationship of the Level of Knowledge when Grouped According to Demographic Variables

A significant association of ($p < 0.05$) between all socio-demographic variables of the respondents and their level of knowledge has been established in this study. Moreover, among all variables General weighted average (GWA) was the only one who had a significance on their level of knowledge ($p < 0.05$). The other variables which are age, sex and type of course (Science or Non-science) although having a minimal difference, their relationship lack statistical significance. In this light, these factors should be taken into account when planning a program to raise the level of knowledge of people in a certain community. Although there is a weak negative correlation (-0.09) between **age and the total knowledge score**, this implies that younger individuals may possess slightly higher knowledge levels compared to older counterparts, yet the difference is minimal. Studies have shown that age and knowledge regarding appropriate antibiotic use differ, with older people in Malaysia and Indonesia (60–80 years old) having less understanding than younger age groups (Kong et al., 2019; Yunita et al., 2022) but those 18 to 34 years old in India and Singapore demonstrated poorer knowledge about antibiotic use than the ≥ 50 years age group (Bhardwaj et al., 2021; Guo et al., 2021).

Similarly, the statistical result showed that in terms of **sex**, males exhibit a slightly higher average knowledge score (53.70%) compared to females (51.82%), but this distinction lacks statistical significance ($t=1.406$, $p=0.161$). Research generally indicates

that women are more knowledgeable about antibiotics and use better practices than males (Yunita et al., 2022; Bhardwaj et al., 2021; Nepal et al., 2019; Waaseth et al., 2019), yet there could be a number of contributing reasons. Some possible factors include the fact that they are typically the primary caregivers for their families, which puts them in contact with healthcare professionals more regularly and, over time, improves their understanding and practices about antibiotics.

There exists a marginal discrepancy in mean knowledge scores among participants enrolled in **science and nonscience courses**. Science courses respondents show an average score of 49.50%, while non-science courses respondents have a slightly higher average of 55.10%. However, this lacks statistical significance ($t = -1.745$, $p = 0.082$), suggesting a trend towards higher knowledge among non-science courses respondents but not reaching conclusive evidence. The overall level of health literacy among university students appears to be insufficient and requires improvement. In terms of course distribution, this observation appears to apply to both health-related and other study courses, though students in health-related study programs tend to have higher levels of health literacy. A variety of factors influence students' health literacy. (Baelen et al., 2021)

Furthermore, an observed weak positive correlation (0.12) between **Grade Weighted Average (GWA) and total knowledge score** suggests that greater academic performance aligns with greater subject knowledge. This finding indicates that students with higher GWAs tend to exhibit higher levels of knowledge compared to their counterparts with lower GWAs. Notably, this correlation achieves statistical significance at the $p < 0.05$ level. A weakly positive association (0.12) was observed between the Grade Weighted Average (GWA) and the total knowledge score. This shows that there is a positive correlation between performance in school and knowledge level and that students with higher GWAs tend to have higher levels of subject knowledge opposed to those with lower GWAs (Nguyen et al., 2022).

Health Promotion Plan for College Students on the Use of Doxycycline as a Prophylaxis For Leptospirosis

On a worldwide basis, a collaborative effort is necessary to address leptospirosis, which includes avoiding wading in floods, wearing protective equipment, and using chemoprophylaxis. Similarly, the Department of Health (DOH) in the Philippines has implemented various preventive measures such as distributing doxycycline in health centers and partner hospitals, conducting awareness campaigns, and providing guidance on proper hygiene to combat the spread of leptospirosis, especially during severe flooding events.

In response to the findings that there is a low knowledge regarding the use of doxycycline for the prevention of leptospirosis, researchers have developed a health promotion program titled "LEAP-TO-spirosis Prevention: Be Safe with Doxycycline". This health promotion program aims to raise awareness of the transmission process and its crucial virulence factors, impart knowledge, and emphasize the importance of

understanding mitigating risks, as most of the college students in Pampanga are not aware of the use of doxycycline as prophylaxis for leptospirosis prevention.

Conclusions

The study examined the respondents' demographic profiles, level of knowledge regarding doxycycline as a prophylaxis for leptospirosis, and the relationship between their awareness and demographic variables. The findings revealed that the average age of respondents was 20.29 years, ranging from 18 to 24 years, with variations in antibiotic knowledge observed among different age groups, aligning with studies from India and Singapore. The respondents' academic performance, with an average General Weighted Average (GWA) of 88.87, suggests a potential correlation between academic standing and level of knowledge regarding doxycycline. Additionally, sex differences in antibiotic knowledge were noted, with existing research indicating that women generally exhibit greater awareness and better practices. Respondents were categorized into science and non-science courses, enabling an analysis of how academic backgrounds influence knowledge levels. The inclusion of leptospirosis history helped determine prior exposure to the disease, with most respondents having no personal or familial history of infection. Risk perception varied, with a minority considering themselves at risk, suggesting that environmental factors such as flood-prone areas influence perceived susceptibility. Awareness activities on leptospirosis were limited, highlighting the need for broader dissemination of educational programs. Regarding doxycycline chemoprophylaxis, nearly half of the respondents had heard of its use, indicating partial awareness but underscoring the need for enhanced education on its preventive role.

The study further assessed the respondents' knowledge levels on doxycycline use for leptospirosis prevention, revealing an average knowledge score of 52.48% (SD = 12.44%), classified as low based on Bloom's criteria. While nearly all respondents demonstrated high awareness of basic preventive measures such as wearing protective footwear, knowledge about doxycycline remained limited. Given that leptospirosis can be acquired through multiple exposure routes, including contaminated water, mucous membranes, and skin abrasions, it is crucial to enhance public understanding of antibiotic prophylaxis. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends doxycycline as a preventive measure for high-risk populations, emphasizing its role in reducing infection rates and preventing severe complications. Previous studies support the effectiveness of mass antibiotic prophylaxis in minimizing leptospirosis cases following high-risk exposures.

Moreover, the study explored the relationship between awareness levels and socio-demographic variables, including age, GWA, sex, and course. The findings suggest that demographic factors influence knowledge levels, reinforcing the importance of targeted educational interventions. Based on these results, an appropriate health promotion program should focus on increasing awareness through accessible and engaging educational campaigns, integrating doxycycline information into existing health programs, and ensuring that preventive measures are effectively communicated to college students. Expanding awareness activities and improving accessibility to doxycycline in flood-prone areas are crucial steps in mitigating leptospirosis risks among

students and the broader community.

Recommendations

This study highlights the low level of knowledge among Pampanga college students regarding leptospirosis prevention using doxycycline, contributing to rising cases in the Philippines. The researchers recommend the following:

- **General public:** Increase awareness through reliable sources, community health seminars, and proactive prevention strategies. Educate the public on doxycycline access and proper usage while promoting environmental sanitation to minimize leptospirosis risks.
- **Health education and promotion officers:** Implement targeted educational campaigns, correct misconceptions, and conduct assessments to improve public awareness and preventive measures.
- **Healthcare providers:** Educate patients on proper doxycycline use, integrate preventive guidance in consultations, and ensure accessibility in healthcare facilities, especially in rural areas.
- **Policy makers and regulators:** Develop policies to improve access to doxycycline, subsidize it in flood-prone areas, and enhance public awareness initiatives.
- **Future researchers:** Expand studies to include diverse demographics, increase sample sizes, and validate health promotion plans with expert consultation for more effective leptospirosis prevention strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study strictly adhered to ethical research standards, ensuring compliance with informed consent procedures, respondents' autonomy, and data confidentiality. Informed consent was obtained through a bilingual consent form presented at the beginning of the questionnaire, requiring respondents to voluntarily agree before participation. Respondents retained the right to withdraw from the study at any time without having to provide justification. Anonymity was maintained, and all collected data were treated with the highest level of confidentiality, strictly used for research purposes in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

In the event of a data breach, the University Research Ethics Board, university administrators, and affected respondents would be notified within 72 hours, following appropriate legal and institutional procedures. Data was securely stored in a restricted-access file, accessible only to authorized researchers, and preserved for a minimum of three years before being permanently deleted in compliance with institutional policies. The deletion process was documented to ensure transparency and accountability.

Furthermore, the study was conducted with the utmost integrity, ensuring the absence of conflicts of interest, strictly avoiding plagiarism, and maintaining objectivity in data interpretation. Findings were presented in an unbiased manner, reinforcing the study's commitment to ethical and methodological standards suitable for academic publication.

REFERENCES

- Asante, C. W., Ackah, C. G., & Frimpong, L. K. (2023). Gender differences in academic performance of students studying science technology engineering and mathematics (STEM) subjects at the University of Ghana. *SN Soc Sci.* 2023;3(1):12. Retrieved from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36686568/>
- Baelen et al. (2021) *SciSpace*. Retrieved from <https://typeset.io/papers>
- Barnacha, L. M. et al. (2023). Licensure examination for certified public accountants, predictive validity of undergraduates' general weighted average on licensure examination for certified public accountants subjects to LECPA results. http://urdc.usl.edu.ph/papers/abar/volume10_s2023/abar_vol10_s2023_p2.pdf?fclid=IwAR0o-CvrlIuDN6-VGA5Gv-PQv7ncEAtpAOW20miPJULbgC6BqmZk7SFkjKc
- Bhardwaj, P., Bhardwaj, N., & Nayak, R. (2021). Knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding antibiotic use among general public in India. *International Journal of Basic & Clinical Pharmacology*, 10(3), 243-249.
- Cebu, J. (2023) (PDF) self-efficacy of Filipino college students as correlates to demographics. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/368789042_Self-Efficacy_of_Filipino_College_Students_as_Correlates_to_Demographics
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2024). Leptospirosis. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/leptospirosis>
- Department of Health. (2023). Leptospirosis surveillance report. Retrieved from <https://doh.gov.ph>
- Fonseka, C. L., Pathirage, S. M., & Wijesinghe, G. K. (2019). Awareness and use of doxycycline for leptospirosis prophylaxis among agricultural workers. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 19(1), 673.
- Goarant, C. (2016) Leptospirosis: Risk factors and management challenges in developing countries, *Research and reports in tropical medicine*. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6028063/>
- Gompf, S. G. (2021). Doxycycline prophylaxis for leptospirosis: A review of effectiveness and recommendations. *Infectious Disease Clinics of North America*, 35(2), 329-341.
- Guo et al. (2021). The associations between poor antibiotic and antimicrobial resistance knowledge and inappropriate antibiotic use in the general population are modified by age. *Antibiotics*, 11(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11010047>
- Kong et al. (2019). Knowledge and expectations on antibiotic use among older adults in Malaysia: A Cross-Sectional Survey. *MDPI*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geriatrics4040061>
- Kozue, T. et al. (2022). Antibiotic prophylaxis for leptospirosis, *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. Edited by Cochrane Hepato-Biliary Group. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8879687/#CD014959-bbs2-0079>
- Nepal, G., Bhandari, R., & Sharma, A. (2019). Knowledge and practice on antibiotic use among pharmacy students. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy*, 41(4), 1036-1043.

- Nguyen, T. et al. (2022). Predicting academic performance with an assessment of students' knowledge of the benefits of high-level and low-level construal. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*. 14(4):194855062210900. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360698661_Predicting_Academic_Performance_with_an_Assessment_of_Students'_Knowledge_of_the_Benefits_of_High-Level_and_Low-Level_Construal
- Rahim, M. A. A. et al. (2018) Effectiveness of antibiotic prophylaxis for leptospirosis among adults: A systematic review, *Malaysian Journal of Applied Sciences*. Retrieved from <https://journal.unisza.edu.my/myjas/index.php/myjas/article/view/144>
- Rajapakse, S. (2022). Diagnosis and treatment of leptospirosis: An updated review. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 75(5), 857-866.
- Waaseth, M. et al. (2019) Knowledge of antibiotics and antibiotic resistance among Norwegian pharmacy customers – a cross-sectional study - *BMC public health*, BioMed Central. Retrieved from <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-019-6409-x>
- World Health Organization. (2003). *Human leptospirosis: Guidance for diagnosis, surveillance, and control*. Geneva: WHO.
- World Health Organization. (2022). *Health promotion and disease prevention*. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int>
- Yunita et al. (2022) Knowledge and practices related to antibiotic use among women in Malang, Indonesia. Retrieved from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36353493/>